

Effect of different crop residue management practices on rice yield.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1993	1994
Rice and wheat straw removed (control)	5.6	4.6
Rice straw burned and wheat straw removed	5.6	4.7
Only rice straw incorporated	5.7	4.7
Only rice straw incorporated with 20 kg N ha ⁻¹	5.7	4.9
Only rice straw incorporated and excess 20 kg N ha ⁻¹ to wheat	5.7	4.8
Rice and wheat straw incorporated	5.9	5.0
Rice and wheat straw incorporated with 20 kg N ha ⁻¹	6.1	5.1
Only rice straw incorporated with berseem	5.8	5.0
20 t FYM ^a before rice	6.7	5.4
20 t FYM ^a before wheat	5.9	5.0
Sesbania aculeata before rice	6.9	5.7
Berseem before wheat	5.8	4.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	.15	.23

^aFYM = farmyard manure.

90 and 83 kg N ha⁻¹ in 1993 and 1994, respectively. Rice straw was incorporated or burned before the wheat crop.

Twenty-two-day-old seedlings of Pant Dhan 10 was transplanted on 24 Jul 1993 and 7 Jul 1994. The recommended fertilizer dose of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied in all plots and the usual cultural operations were done.

Burning of rice straw was at par with the treatment where straw was removed. Incorporating both rice and wheat straw gave significantly higher yield over rice alone because wheat straw supplied some extra nutrient to the rice crop. Incorporating straw with a starter dose of 20 kg N was slightly better than the treatment without a starter dose because the initial dose helped straw to decompose faster, thereby providing more nutrients to rice.

Green manuring with *S. aculeata* gave the highest production and was at par with 20 t farmyard manure ha⁻¹ before rice. Use of GM berseem gave a slightly better yield than the control. The higher grain yield obtained from incorporating straw with a starter dose of N, FYM, and GM with *S. aculeata* was attributed to extra N (more than 120 kg ha⁻¹) applied to these treatments. Besides the direct contribution of N, the better soil physical condition must have positively contributed to yield. ■

Evaluation of green manures and grain legumes

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We compared several green manures and grain legumes in terms of dry weight, N percentage, and N accumulation at 60 d after sowing in two seasons, Jul-Sep 1991 and Feb-May 1992. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with, three replications.

Dry matter production and N accumulation in green manures and grain legumes at 60 DAS.^a Coimbatore, India.

Green manure	Jul-Sep 1991			Feb-May 1992		
	Dry weight (t ha ⁻¹)	N (%)	N accumulation (kg ha ⁻¹)	Dry weight (t ha ⁻¹)	N (%)	N accumulation (kg ha ⁻¹)
<i>S. aculeata</i>	5.4	1.7	91.8	8.6	1.6	137.6
<i>S. rostrata</i>	4.6	2.4	110.4	7.5	2.2	165.0
<i>S. speciosa</i>	1.6	1.7	27.2	6.5	2.1	136.5
<i>S. grandiflora</i>	2.4	1.2	28.8	7.2	1.4	100.8
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	1.4	1.2	16.2	5.0	0.9	45.0
<i>Glycine max</i>	2.0	1.1	22.0	8.1	1.0	81.0
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	5.8	1.3	75.4	9.3	1.2	107.0
<i>Phaseolus trilobus</i>	3.8	1.5	55.1	9.5	1.2	114.0
<i>Vigna aureus</i>	2.1	1.5	31.1	8.4	1.0	84.0
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	5.8	1.4	77.6	10.0	1.2	123.0
CD	0.61	0.62	3.8	3.5	1.0	5.2

^aDAS = days after sowing.

Effect of soil amendments on rice yield

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We conducted a field experiment on a Typic Natrustalf at GBPUAT in the 1987-92 wet seasons (WS) to evaluate the performance of gypsum, pyrite, mud press, and farmyard manure (FYM) as soil amendments.

Surface soil (0-15 cm) is silty clay loam (53.5% sand, 25.2% silt, and 21.3% clay), with pH 9.4-9.8, EC 6.9 dS m⁻¹, 22.6% exchangeable Na, 0.12% organic C, 8.2 kg Olsen P ha⁻¹, 0.35 c mol exchangeable K kg⁻¹, and CEC 12.4 c mol kg⁻¹.

All of the green manures and grain legumes recorded higher dry matter production in the February-May season. *Sesbania rostrata* accumulated more N (165 kg ha⁻¹) than did the other green manures.

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) outperformed the other grain legumes, producing 10 t green manure on dry-weight basis.

After the rice harvest in January, farmers may grow *S. aculeata* or *S. rostrata* in situ and plow it down during transplanting of the next rice crop that is grown during kuruvai season (June-September). ■

Amendments were applied in Apr 1987 and 35-d-old seedlings (3 hill⁻¹) of rice cultivar Saket 4 were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing. A uniform dose of 150 kg N had in three splits, 21.8 kg P ha⁻¹, 4 1.5 kg K ha⁻¹, and 25 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹ (basal), was applied. A wheat crop was raised in the rabi (winter) season, with 150 kg N applied in 3 splits, 26.2 kg P, and 41.5 kg K (basal) ha⁻¹. The same rice - wheat cropping sequence and NPK fertilization were followed during subsequent years on the same layout without additional soil amendments.

The control treatment had an average rice yield of 2.7 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). The higher yields recorded were with gypsum application at 12 t ha⁻¹ followed by pyrite at 4 t ha⁻¹. The lowest yield increase over the control was observed with pyrite at 2 t ha⁻¹, mud press at 6 t ha⁻¹, and FYM at 20 t ha⁻¹.

Table 1. Effects of soil amendments on rice yield. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987-92.

Soil amendment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)						Six-year average			
	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	Rice		Wheat	
							Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over control (%)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over control (%)
Control	0.9	2.2	2.8	3.1	3.5	3.8	2.7	–	1.2	–
Gypsum (6 t ha ⁻¹)	1.8	3.1	3.5	3.8	4.1	4.3	3.4	25.9	2.0	66.7
Gypsum (9 t ha ⁻¹)	2.2	3.4	3.8	4.1	4.5	4.8	3.8	40.7	2.4	100.0
Gypsum (12 t ha ⁻¹)	2.6	3.8	4.2	4.6	4.9	5.1	4.2	55.6	2.9	141.7
Pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	1.3	2.5	3.0	3.3	3.7	3.9	3.0	11.1	1.7	41.7
Pyrite (3 t ha ⁻¹)	1.6	2.9	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.0	3.1	14.8	1.9	58.3
Pyrite (4 t ha ⁻¹)	2.5	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.5	4.6	3.9	44.4	2.5	108.3
Mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	1.5	2.7	3.1	3.4	3.7	3.8	3.0	11.1	1.7	41.7
Mud press (12 t ha ⁻¹)	1.7	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.1	4.3	3.4	25.9	2.0	66.7
FYM ^a (20 t ha ⁻¹)	1.4	2.7	2.9	3.3	3.6	3.9	3.0	11.1	1.5	25.0
FYM (10 t) + pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	2.2	3.2	3.6	3.9	4.2	4.4	3.6	33.3	2.0	66.7
FYM (10 t) + mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	2.4	3.3	3.7	4.1	4.3	4.5	3.7	37.0	2.2	83.3
SEM (±)	0.12	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.016	–	–	–	–
LSD (5%)	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	–	–	–	–

^aFYM = farmyard manure.

Table 2. Physicochemical properties of surface soil (0-15 cm)^a after 6 yr of experimentation. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987-92.

Treatment	pH (1:2 soil-water ratio)	EC (dSm ⁻¹) (1:2 soil-water ratio)	CEC (c mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable cations (c mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)				Exchangeable sodium percentage
				Na ⁺	K	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺	
Control	8.2	0.40	12.0	0.58	0.19	5.27	1.27	4.83
Gypsum (6 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.36	12.1	0.42	0.12	7.00	1.20	3.50
Gypsum (9 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.33	12.0	0.41	0.11	7.13	1.00	3.45
Gypsum (12 t ha ⁻¹)	7.3	0.33	12.0	0.40	0.11	7.47	1.13	3.13
Pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	8.2	0.36	12.1	0.49	0.16	6.80	1.27	3.95
Pyrite (3 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.34	12.1	0.43	0.14	7.00	1.10	3.58
Pyrite (4 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.35	12.2	0.40	0.12	7.10	1.00	3.28
Mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.35	12.1	0.40	0.13	6.73	1.00	3.28
Mud press (12 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.29	11.8	0.39	0.12	7.20	1.27	3.31
FYM (20 t ha ⁻¹)	7.7	0.30	12.3	0.42	0.19	6.13	0.93	3.44
FYM (10 t) + pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	8.0	0.33	12.0	0.39	0.19	6.67	1.00	3.22
FYM (10 t) + mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	7.7	0.32	12.1	0.38	0.16	7.47	0.86	3.22
SEM (±)		0.02		0.03	0.03	0.29	0.13	–
LSD (5%)		ns ^b		0.09	ns	0.84	ns	–

^aThe Initial values were pH 9.4-9.8, EC 6.9 dS m⁻¹, CEC 12.4 cmol(p⁺) kg⁻¹, and ESP 22.6. ^bns = not significant.

Applying FYM at 10 t ha⁻¹ in combination with pyrite at 2 t ha⁻¹ or gypsum at 6 t ha⁻¹ resulted in comparable yields. The amendments were effective in this order: gypsum > pyrite > mud press > FYM.

Wheat yield averaged 1.2 t ha⁻¹ in the control treatment (Table 1). Maximum yield increase was observed with gypsum application at 12 t ha⁻¹ and minimum with FYM at 20 t ha⁻¹. The pattern of effectiveness of soil amendments in the wheat crop was similar to that in the rice crop.

After 6 yr, the pH and exchangeable sodium percentage in the control and treated plots were appreciably reduced, and the level of amendment applied was reflected in this reduction (Table 2). Besides the amendments, the rice - wheat cropping sequence has a profound influence on soil improvement, as reflected in the yield levels from year 1 to year 6. Gypsum alone or gypsum with FYM outperformed pyrite. ■

Crop management

Use of deepwater varietal mixtures to minimize hydrological risk in basin lands of Bihar, India

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Chours (basin lands) are low-lying fields of variable shape and size having poor or no drainage. Crop production depends mainly on the unpredictable monsoon rainfall. Drought or flooding of varying durations